

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HUEH CHUAH****FIRST NAME: ONG****PROGRAM CODE: MNRJ-R****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
5. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
8. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

ACADEMIC PAPER WRITING WITH CONFIDENCE

1) INTRODUCTION

I have completed two master courses. I also worked in industry as for over 30years. I have held the role of System Integration Engineer, Project Manager and Director. In 10years time, I will be sixty-five years old and will be retiring. The life expectancy for Singapore in 2019 was 83.53 years, a 0.16% increase from 2018. For the next 25 to 30 years, I wish to continue in research, encourage the efficient use of energy and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, I decided to continue my Master or PhD study with EUCLID. I am not new in academic paper writing, but I am not an expert in this field. The ACA-401 period one course pack and the video provided me with strong foundations for writing academic paper with confidence. The scope of ACA-401 period one is well organized and covered many importance areas like evidence-based essay writing, literature review, handling and prevention of plagiarism, style guide, proofreading, etc. (EUCLID 2019 1-4, 5-12, 17-22).

2) EVIDENCE-BASED ESSAY

On the Basics of Essay Writing by University of New South Wales (EUCLID 2019, 1-4), it is recommended an academic essay should include supporting evidence. My country Singapore has also passed the Protection from Online Falsehoods and Manipulation Bill in October 2019. This dictates websites to run government “correction notices” alongside content it deems false. This is another example of growing concerns over the spreading of fake news and misinformation. It is my responsibility to write academic essay with supporting evidences and not to fabricate research findings unethically. By doing so, I hope to fulfil Section 7 of the Protection of Online Falsehoods and Manipulation Act Requirement. For non-compliance, it is a heavy price to pay. Individuals that are found in breach of Section 7 will be liable to a fine up to S\$50,000 and/or a term of imprisonment up to 5years. For tech companies who run online media platforms, a fine of up to S\$500,000 will be imposed. This reflected zero tolerance of Singapore Government towards fake news and misinformation. Writing an article and imagine getting into jail for up to 5 years is not something that writers can accept easily. Luckily the evidence-based writers in Singapore will not be affected. Is Singapore Government stern approach in controlling fake or non-evidence based information or news the best approach for other countries to follow? If not, what other methods can prevent spreading of fake news? Exchange of information and sharing of the lesson learnt of the process/system adopted by different countries will help to reduce cost in innovation, reduce system implementation errors, and will help in improving the overall system performance timely.

3) PLAGIARISM

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma defined “Plagiarism when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” (EUCLID 2019, 5) However, Cleenewerck did not identify the root cause of the plagiarism. These factors influencing plagiarism in higher education according to Eva Jereb et al. can be classified as ease of use of Information Communication Technologies and Web, regulation, academic skills, teaching factors, pressure, pride and other reasons (Eva Jereb et al. 2018, 5-7). To prevent plagiarism, Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma has identified various methods used to indicate where a piece of information came from (EUCLID 2019, 6-10).

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review as presented focused more on micro-level details and after reading, I am not able to learn the right process or procedures for conducting a literature review. It also did not define literature review and explain how to do a systematic literature review. These steps of literature review are choosing a review topic, searching and selecting appropriate articles, analysing and synthesizing the literature and organization of

writing the review (Abdullah Ramdhani et al. 2014, 50-54). Hannah Snyder further elaborated different type of Literature Review: Systematic literature review, semi-systematic review, integrative review (Hannah Snyder 2019, 334-336). Regardless the method or process that is being used, I advocate to have the Literature Research conduct efficiently.

5) RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 DEVELOP INTERNATIONAL STANDARD

The process of writing academic essay or paper must be established as an international standard across all industries worldwide. With a proper standard that is recognized worldwide, this will be a controlled process for different organizations and academic institutions in different countries. This is no different from the different IEC standards for engineering design, testing or certification I used to use for getting my product design and develop from conceptualization to commercialization. According to ISO “International Standards mean that consumers can have confidence that the products are reliable and of good quality”. The benefits for businesses, which embrace ISO standards are reliability, improved performance, better quality, increased revenue, risk reduction, sustainability and innovation.

5.2 PROMOTE EFFICIENT PROCESS

The process of writing academic paper must be as efficient as possible. For example, the Master/PhD Students must know how to conduct literature review efficiently. The University of Oregon has summarized the best practices and useful advice on becoming a more productive faculty writer. Kevin J. Heintz has presented essential guidelines for writing an effective research paper (Kevin J. Heintz 2018, 1-2). Ten years ago, the software writer has to do coding line by line. Today, the technology has developed that the engineer just need to do the flowchart, and there is autocode generator that can takeover and do the coding. I used to do testing of software code line by line, there is also a mandatory from company management to develop an automatic software test program to replace the manual work of testing the code. If engineers can do it, I do not see there will be problems for academic writers to do it. In future, will there be an academic paper writing machine with writer just input their main ideas for the paper? It is also a major improvement in productivity if we can develop an efficient process where all international writers can reduce the paper writing duration from 3 months to 3 weeks or from 6 months to 6 weeks. Whether this trend will be developed in future depends very much on the will of the various research organizations, academic institutions, private organizations from different countries. Once this procedure is developed across different industries, the task force must continue improve the procedure and system.

5.3 FOCUS ON PRODUCING QUALITY PAPER

Ransom Patterson has supported this recommendation of writing high quality papers and essays quickly (Ransom Patterson 2019, 1-2). Suny Empore State College in Qualities of Academic Writing has stressed a few important points for quality writing. These are write to learn, go deep and be willing to change direction, use a method valued in the discipline the writer are writing in, ask questions that matter, argue, provide evidence, document the sources of evidence. All these are calling the writers to produce quality papers. If the paper written is of low quality, it will not worth spending our precious time to read.

6) CONCLUSION

The paper has many good information for Master/PhD Students who want to write academic paper. It is recommended to write evidence-based essay and not to fabricate research findings. In Singapore, non-evidence-based essay writers or online media companies will face fine or jail if found not complying to Section 7 of Protection of Online Falsehoods and Manipulation Act.

On Plagiarism, understand the factors influencing of Plagiarism (Eva Jereb et al. 2018, 5-7) and cite the sources are best practice to tackle or prevent Plagiarism.

We have identified steps of Literature Review and helped researchers/students to understand different types of literature review.

We recommended three improvement areas related to academic essay or paper writing such as to develop international standard for all writers worldwide to comply with and continue make improvement on the standard for writing paper, promote efficient process in academic writing and focus on producing quality academic papers.

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